

Revolutionizing Pedagogy: Navigating the Integration of Digital Technologies in Teaching and Learning for Learners with Disabilities in Zambia

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ABSTRACT

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The study explored the experiences of teachers on integration of digital technologies in teaching and learning for learners with disabilities in special education. A qualitative case study design was employed and expert purposive sampling was used on twenty ICT specialist teachers in schools. Also, data was collected using structured interviews and classroom observations which was thematically analysed. The study revealed that integration of digital technologies enhanced accessibility, engagement, and personalized learning for learners with disabilities, allowing them to participate more fully in educational activities. On the other hand, challenges such as insufficient infrastructure, lack of teacher training, and limited access to adaptive devices hinder the full potential of digital tools. Based on these findings, there is need to effectively revolutionize pedagogy through the integration of digital technologies for learners with disabilities, schools should implement comprehensive professional development programs that equip teachers with the skills to utilize adaptive and assistive technologies, ensuring inclusive, personalized, and engaging learning experiences for all students.

KEYWORDS:

Accessibility, Digital Technologies, Engagement, Integration, Pedagogy, and Personalized Learning

INTRODUCTION

Recent studies have shown numerous models and theories of technology integration among teachers, apart from which, this study intended to take a step forward on how this technology integration has enhanced further in developing teaching practices in the form of teacher learning, pedagogical strategies, teacher performance, and student engagement. The challenge lies in inculcating innovative teaching methods to align with students' tech-savvy preferences, emphasizing the importance of educators to embrace the technology.

In the 21st century technology integration signifies the importance in education for effective teaching and learning (Mtebe & Raphael, 2018; Wright & Akgunduz, 2018). The integration of digital technologies in education has been recognized as a critical factor in enhancing teaching and learning, particularly for learners with disabilities (UNESCO, 2021). In Zambia, the Zambia Information and

Communications Technology Authority (ZICTA) has supported special schools by providing digital technologies to promote inclusive education. However, despite these efforts, the extent to which these technologies are effectively integrated into teaching and learning for learners with disabilities remains unclear.

Research suggests that while digital tools have the potential to improve accessibility and engagement for learners with disabilities, challenges such as inadequate teacher training, lack of technical support, and infrastructure limitations often hinder effective implementation (WHO & World Bank, 2011). According to Alper and Goggin (2017), "the success of digital inclusion for learners with disabilities depends not only on access to technology but also on the ability to use it effectively within pedagogical frameworks" (p. 310). Therefore, it is essential to explore how ZICTA-supported special schools navigate the integration of digital technologies, identifying both opportunities and barriers that affect teaching and learning outcomes.

Additionally, studies indicate that while assistive technologies can significantly improve learning experiences, their benefits are often limited by the lack of contextualized policies and implementation strategies (Seale, 2014). Without a clear understanding of how these digital resources are being utilized in ZICTA-supported special schools, there is a risk of

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underutilization or ineffective application, which may compromise the goal of inclusive education. As Burns, Kimmitt, and McArdle (2022) argue, "the mere presence of digital technologies does not automatically translate to meaningful inclusion; rather, it is the pedagogical approaches and institutional support that determine their impact. Given these concerns, this study seeks to explore how digital technologies are being integrated into teaching and learning for learners with disabilities in ZICTA-supported special schools in Zambia. By examining the experiences of educators and learners, the study aims to identify best practices, challenges, and potential strategies to enhance the effective use of digital technologies in inclusive education.

One of the theories adopted in this paper is the extension of Social Cognitive Theory that is Bandura's Self-Efficacy Theory. It offers insight into how individual think or judge about their own skills and how they gather information through social interactions. According to this, teacher's thinking, feelings (Karolčik & Čipková, 2017) in their own talents impact their motivation and behaviour. Teachers' self-efficacy views may have an influence on how eager they are to integrate technology into the classroom (Akturk & Ozturk, 019; Njiku et al., 2022). Regarding the use of technology, self-efficacy is one of the personality traits that may help teachers attain their full potential in terms of both their career prospects and the successful integration of technologies into their regular teaching techniques. The teachers must be confident in their capacity to do so in order to accomplish this (Njiku et al., 2022; Wright & Akgunduz, 2018).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study employed a qualitative case study design to explore the integration of digital technologies in teaching and learning for learners with disabilities in ZICTA-supported special schools. The study utilised purposive expert purposive sampling was used to select twenty ICT-Specialist Teachers (ST) for learners with disabilities as key participants, ensuring that those who have first-hand experience with the phenomenon under investigation are included (Creswell & Poth, 2018). Two ZICTA-supported institution from each province were used. Data was collected through semi-structured interviews, and classroom observations, methods that allow for a rich, detailed understanding of participants' experiences and perceptions (Merriam & Tisdell, 2016). Data was analysed using thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) framework to identify key patterns and emerging themes. Ethical considerations, including informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation, were upheld to ensure the integrity of the study and the protection of participants.

FINDINGS

When participants were asked on how has digital technologies enhanced or challenged the teaching and learning experiences of learners with disabilities in your school. Participants noted that digital technologies have significantly improved access to curriculum content and enhanced engagement among learners with disabilities. However, challenges such as lack of resources, inadequate teacher training, and poor infrastructure have limited the full potential of these technologies in inclusive classrooms.

Improved Accessibility and Engagement

The study findings established that digital technology enhanced the teaching and learning experiences of learners with disabilities in your school through Improved accessibility and engagement. In support ST-4 noted that: *"The introduction of screen readers and audio books has helped our blind learners access the same materials as others, and they're more motivated now."*

Contributing on the same findings the above, ST-2 added that: *"With digital tools like screen readers and text-to-speech software, our visually impaired learners can now access textbooks and notes without waiting for someone to read to them."*

Findings of the study further revealed that *"Tablets allow learners with learning disabilities to revisit lessons at their own pace, which was not possible before. Tablets with interactive learning apps have made lessons more engaging for my learners with autism. They respond better to visuals and animations."* (ST-3)

Yet ST-15 said: *"Since we introduced tablets with learning apps, our learners with dyslexia can now follow lessons using audio support and interactive visuals it keeps them focused and more involved in class activities."*

In support, HT-16 said: *"For our visually impaired learners, screen readers and magnification tools have opened up a whole new world. They can now read notes and participate in group tasks without always relying on a teacher or peer."*

Also, ST-11 revealed that *"Engagement has really improved. Learners who used to lose interest during lessons are now more alert and curious because digital content is more interactive and adapted to their pace and style of learning."*

Improved Communication and Interaction

The study established that the digital technology enhanced improved communication and interaction during teaching and learning for learners with disabilities in your school. In support ST-19 revealed that *"Learners who are non-verbal now use communication apps on tablets to express their needs and participate in class discussions. Technology has given a voice to them who previously couldn't communicate easily. It has also strengthened the bond between teachers and learners."*

Contributing to the same subject; ST-7 during interview had this to say: *"Before we introduced tablets with*

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communication apps, some of our non-verbal learners struggled to express themselves. Now they can use icons and pictures to tell us what they need or how they feel.”

Contributing to the same subject; during the interviews HT-3 lamented that

“Learners with hearing impairments are now able to follow lessons better using captioned videos and sign language interpretation tools. It has made a huge difference in how they interact during discussions. “One of my learners with cerebral palsy couldn’t speak clearly, but now he uses a speech-generating device to answer questions in class. It’s helped him participate more actively and confidently.”

On the same, ST-8 had this to say: “Even shy learners or those with autism spectrum conditions feel more comfortable using digital platforms to contribute to class discussions. It gives them a voice in a way that’s less overwhelming.”

In support of the findings above, ST-1 had this to say: “The real-time messaging and collaboration tools we use allow learners to work in groups without the pressure of speaking out loud. They can type, draw, or use emojis to communicate.”

On the same, ST-4 had this to say: “Parents have also told us that their children talk more about what they have learned now because they can demonstrate it using their learning devices at home.”

Enhanced Learner Independence and Participation

The other findings of the study indicated that digital technology enhanced learner independence and participation during teaching and learning for learners with disabilities in your school. In buttressing the submission above, ST-5 asserted that: “One of my learners with a physical disability can now write assignments using voice-to-text software. He no longer needs constant assistance.”

This was evidenced by ST-2 who explained that: *Digital tools have given some of our learners more independence. They can research and complete tasks at their own pace. When learners use assistive tech independently, you can see how proud they are. It boosts their self-esteem.*

In support of this, ST-16 had this to say: “Some learners who used to be withdrawn are now eager to participate because they can work using tools that support their needs.”

Personalized and Adaptive Learning

The findings highlighted personalized and adaptive learning due to digital technology enhancement in the teaching and learning for learners with disabilities in your school. In support of the findings above, ST-4 had this to say: “The educational apps we use can be tailored to each learner’s pace and level. This has really helped those who struggle to keep up in a traditional classroom.”

Contributing to the same subject; ST-8 had this to say: “Some learners with autism respond better to the structured and

predictable nature of learning apps. It reduces their anxiety and improves focus.”

Also, ST-5 commented that: “The educational software we use adjusts the difficulty level automatically based on each learner’s performance, so even those with learning challenges can progress at their own pace without feeling left behind.”

For instance, ST-7 explained that: “Some of our learners with autism benefit from structured routines. The apps allow us to create personalized schedules and tasks, which has helped reduce anxiety and improve focus during lessons.”

Contributing on the same, ST-13 said: “With digital tools, I can assign different tasks to different learners depending on their needs. For example, one learner might get visual instructions while another uses audio this was hard to manage before we had the technology.”

Teacher Capacity and Digital Literacy Gaps

On the other hand, during the data analysis findings revealed the challenges faced by specialist teachers in the teaching and learning for learners with disabilities in your school using digital technology. In support of this, ST-5 indicated: “Sometimes the technology is there, but we the teachers are not well trained to use it effectively for learners with special needs.”

Contributing to the same subject; ST-3 during interview had this to say: “We had smartboards installed, but I feel I still lack confidence in adapting lessons using the features they offer for inclusive learning.”

Participant ST-6 submitted that: “As teachers, we haven’t received proper training on how to use digital tools for learners with disabilities. We mostly rely on trial and error. Sometimes the technology is there, but we don’t know how to integrate it into inclusive teaching strategies.”

Another ST-17 had this to say: *we need continuous professional development (CPD) for teachers on how to integrate digital tools into inclusive pedagogy. Workshops focused on digital content creation tailored for diverse learning needs. Also, training on how to select, use, and troubleshoot assistive technologies effectively.*

Similarly, ST-4 pointed out that: *Teachers may not have sufficient training in using assistive technologies or integrating digital tools effectively into their lessons. Some teachers are not confident in troubleshooting digital tools when they malfunction.*

Infrastructure and Resource Limitations

Another challenge that was highlighted was the lack of infrastructure and due to resource limitations. In support of the findings above, ST-14 had this to say: “Most of the devices we have are not enough, so not every learner with a disability gets access during lessons.”

Also, participant ST-10 indicated that: “Power outages and poor internet connectivity make it hard to rely on digital tools all the time.”

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This confirmed by participant HT-8 during interviews: *“we experience frequent power outages, slow internet, or lack of ICT support staff in schools can hinder digital learning* Similarly, ST-3) said, *“Unreliable electricity and internet really make it difficult to use digital tools consistently, especially in rural areas.”*

In contribution the participant ST-5 had this to say: *“Most of the digital tools we have are not disability-friendly. For example, we don’t have devices with Braille displays or software tailored for learners with hearing impairments.”*

One participant ST-12 shared, *“Only a few learners can access the assistive devices at a time. We simply don’t have enough for everyone who needs them.”*

Further participants were asked on what improvements or additional support do you think are needed to maximize the benefits of digital technologies in inclusive education. To maximize the impact of digital technologies in inclusive education, stakeholders emphasized the need for greater investment in assistive devices, teacher training, and infrastructure. Equally important is the development of inclusive digital content, policy support, and stronger partnerships to ensure that no learner is left behind.

Need for More Training and Capacity Building for Teachers

In order improve support to maximize the benefits of digital technologies in inclusive education. The findings showed the need for more training and capacity building for teachers. In conformity with the above findings, participants ST-15 during interviews said that: *“We need regular training on how to use assistive technologies effectively. Most of us are still learning on the job and that limits what we can offer the learners.”*

In support of the findings above, participant ST-4) had this to say: *“Sometimes the technology is available, but without proper guidance on how to adapt it for inclusive learning, it doesn’t serve its full purpose.”*

Also, participant ST-3 indicated that: *“We have the devices, but many of us don’t fully understand how to use them for learners with special needs. We need proper training, not just general ICT workshops.”*

In contribution the participant ST-16) had this to say: *“Sometimes I feel overwhelmed because I’m not sure which apps or tools are best suited for my learners with different disabilities. More targeted training would really help.”*

Similarly, ST-3 said, *“We were given the equipment, but no one showed us how to integrate it into our lesson plans for inclusive education. We’re learning by trial and error, which isn’t ideal.”*

Increased Availability and Accessibility of Digital Devices

The findings showed the need for increased availability and accessibility of digital devices. This was evident from participant ST-5 had this to say: *“We need more devices that are specially designed for learners with disabilities. Right*

now, we’re forced to improvise, and not every learner gets access.”

In support of the above findings, participant ST-11 said: *“There are just not enough resources. One tablet for an entire class of learners with different needs is not enough.”*

Another participant ST-4) indicate that: *“Some of the learners can’t use the standard devices because of their disabilities. We need tools that are specially designed for their needs, like Braille displays or adaptive keyboards.”*

In support of the findings above, participant ST-2 had this to say: *“Access to digital tools shouldn’t be a privilege. Every learner, regardless of ability, should have their own device that supports their learning style and needs.”*

Also, participant ST-15 had this to say: *“We only have a few tablets in the whole school, so learners with disabilities have to take turns or miss out completely. We need more devices to ensure everyone benefits.”*

Another the participant ST-13 had this to say: *There is need for provision of appropriate devices such as screen readers, Braille notetakers, AAC devices, and hearing aids.*

Improved Infrastructure and Technical Support

Further, the findings showed the need for improved infrastructure and technical support. This was evident from participant ST-5 had this to say: *“Power outages and poor internet make it hard to use digital tools consistently. We need stable infrastructure to rely on these technologies.”*

In support of the finding, participant HT-3 had this to say: *Reliable electricity, internet access, and maintenance support in all schools, especially in rural and under-resourced areas.* The participant ST-1 said: *“When devices break or software stops working, we have no one to fix them quickly. We need a dedicated ICT support person in the school.”*

Another the participant ST-3 had this to say: *“Sometimes we want to use the digital tools, but the power goes out or the internet is too weak. Without reliable infrastructure, it’s hard to depend on technology in our lessons.”*

Also, participant ST-20 had this to say: *“When a device stops working or software crashes, we have no one to fix it immediately. We need a technician on-site or at least someone we can call for quick support.”*

Also, Participant ST-1 asserted that, *“The computers are outdated and slow. Even when learners are eager to use them, the experience becomes frustrating. Upgrading the infrastructure would make a big difference.”*

Another the participant ST-4 had this to say: *There is need also to train learners with disabilities on how to use digital tools independently and safely.*

Also, Participant ST-6 asserted that: *we need also to be engaging parents through digital literacy programs so they can support their children’s learning at home.*

DISCUSSION

The study aimed to explore how digital technologies have enhanced or challenged the teaching and learning experiences of learners with disabilities in a school setting. The findings revealed both positive impacts and challenges related to the use of digital technologies in inclusive education. One of the most prominent findings in the study was that digital technologies have significantly enhanced accessibility and engagement for learners with disabilities. Learners who previously struggled with traditional educational methods now benefit from tools like screen readers, interactive apps, and speech recognition software. As one participant noted, *“The introduction of tablets with learning apps has helped our learners with dyslexia follow lessons using audio support and interactive visuals that keeps them focused and more involved in class activities.”* This finding aligns with research by Al-Azawei, Parslow, and Lundqvist (2016), who emphasize that digital technologies, such as text-to-speech and speech recognition tools, play a critical role in making content accessible to learners with disabilities, particularly those with learning disabilities.

Furthermore, the use of digital platforms enables more individualized learning. One teacher shared, *“The educational software we use adjusts the difficulty level automatically based on each learner’s performance, so even those with learning challenges can progress at their own pace without feeling left behind.”* This finding resonates with findings by Bejo and Husain (2020), who highlight that adaptive technologies can create personalized learning environments, allowing students to work at their own pace and ensuring that each learner's unique needs are met.

The findings of this study indicate that digital technologies have significantly enhanced communication and interaction in the teaching and learning experiences of learners with disabilities. Participants highlighted that tools such as speech-generating devices, visual communication apps, and interactive platforms have improved how learners express themselves and engage with both peers and teachers. One teacher shared, *“Some of our non-verbal learners are now able to participate in class using communication apps. It’s amazing to see them finally have a voice.”* This aligns with Alper and Raharinirina (2006), who emphasized that assistive technologies empower learners with communication difficulties to engage more meaningfully in classroom interactions. Additionally, digital platforms that allow for real-time feedback and collaborative learning have helped foster inclusive participation, breaking down barriers that previously hindered interaction. According to Dell, Newton, and Petroff (2016), such technologies facilitate inclusive communication by enabling alternative modes of expression, which is essential in special education contexts. The study therefore supports the growing consensus that digital tools are not only enhancing access but also transforming the social

dynamics of learning environments for learners with disabilities.

The findings of this study revealed that digital technologies have played a pivotal role in enhancing learner independence and participation among learners with disabilities. Participants reported that digital tools such as screen readers, audio instructions, and learning apps enable learners to complete tasks on their own, thereby reducing over-reliance on teacher assistance. One teacher noted, *“Some of our learners are now able to read and answer questions independently with the help of screen readers and voice-to-text software. It has boosted their confidence a lot.”* This observation is supported by Al-Azawei, Serenelli, and Lundqvist (2016), who argue that technology can promote autonomy in learning by allowing students to interact with content in ways that match their abilities. Independent engagement not only empowers learners but also fosters a sense of agency and inclusion in the classroom.

Additionally, digital technologies have been found to enhance personalized and adaptive learning, allowing teachers to tailor content to the unique needs of each learner. Several participants explained that digital platforms with adaptive features automatically adjust learning tasks based on a student’s performance, ensuring that learners are neither overwhelmed nor under-challenged. One educator remarked, *“The software we use adapts to each child’s level, so they move at their own pace without pressure, and it keeps them engaged.”* This aligns with Rose and Meyer’s (2002) Universal Design for Learning (UDL) framework, which promotes the use of flexible technologies to accommodate a wide range of learning preferences and abilities. Personalized learning tools not only meet students at their level but also promote inclusivity by recognizing diverse educational needs within a shared learning space.

Furthermore, the increased learner participation through interactive and gamified platforms has transformed the traditional classroom dynamics. Teachers reported that learners who were previously passive or disengaged are now more involved in lessons thanks to visually rich, interactive content that caters to multiple senses. One teacher stated, *“When we use interactive whiteboards and educational games, even the quietest learners want to participate. It’s more inclusive than chalk-and-talk methods.”* This finding echoes the work of Blackhurst (2005), who highlighted that digital tools can stimulate motivation and active engagement, particularly among learners with disabilities. Thus, the integration of technology not only supports differentiated learning but also cultivates a more inclusive, participatory, and learner-centered environment.

On the other hand, the study highlighted that teachers often lack adequate training in using digital tools effectively for inclusive education. One teacher commented, *“We have the devices, but many of us don’t fully understand how to use them for learners with special needs. We need proper*

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training, not just general ICT workshops.” This challenge is echoed by Hennessy, Harrison, and Wamakote (2010), who argue that teacher training is essential for the effective integration of technology in the classroom. Without proper professional development, teachers may struggle to incorporate technology in ways that meet the diverse needs of learners with disabilities.

While digital technologies hold great potential, several challenges hinder their full integration into the classroom, particularly in schools with limited resources. A significant challenge identified was the inadequate infrastructure, including unreliable electricity and poor internet connectivity. As one participant shared, *“Sometimes we want to use the digital tools, but the power goes out or the internet is too weak. Without reliable infrastructure, it’s hard to depend on technology in our lessons.”* This limitation is consistent with research by Kay (2012), who found that infrastructure issues, particularly in developing regions, pose significant barriers to the successful implementation of digital technologies in education.

However, the findings suggest that several key areas need to be addressed to ensure digital tools are fully effective in supporting learners with disabilities. These areas include teacher training, increased access to specialized devices, and the enhancement of technical infrastructure. The discussion below explores these findings in the context of existing literature.

A prominent theme that emerged from the findings was the need for more specialized training and capacity building for teachers. Teachers reported that although digital tools are available, they often lack the necessary skills to use these technologies effectively for inclusive education. One teacher highlighted, *“We have the devices, but many of us don’t fully understand how to use them for learners with special needs. We need proper training, not just general ICT workshops.”* This finding is consistent with research by Hennessy, Harrison, and Wamakote (2010), who argue that teacher professional development is essential for the successful integration of technology in inclusive classrooms. Without sufficient training, teachers are unable to tailor digital tools to the diverse needs of learners with disabilities, which limits the effectiveness of the technologies. Moreover, further training in adaptive technologies is crucial. As highlighted by Bejo and Husain (2020), many teachers do not know how to select or integrate assistive technologies that could support learners with specific disabilities, such as speech impairments or learning disabilities. The need for targeted, ongoing professional development is critical to bridging this gap in teacher capability.

Another key area identified was the need for more accessible and specialized digital devices. As noted in the findings, many schools lack enough devices, and those available are often not tailored to the specific needs of learners with disabilities. One participant stated, *“We only have a few*

tablets in the whole school, so learners with disabilities have to take turns or miss out completely. We need more devices to ensure everyone benefits.” This limitation in access to appropriate devices is a significant barrier to achieving inclusivity. According to Eynon and Malmberg (2011), the availability of specialized devices, such as those with adaptive interfaces or screen readers, is crucial for ensuring that learners with disabilities can participate fully in the digital learning environment. Without these tools, learners with disabilities are often excluded from opportunities that could enhance their learning experiences.

A critical finding in the study was the need for more accessible and adaptive digital devices to support the diverse needs of learners with disabilities. One participant expressed, *“We only have a few tablets in the whole school, so learners with disabilities have to take turns or miss out completely. We need more devices to ensure everyone benefits.”* This shortage of devices is a significant barrier to the equitable distribution of educational technology in inclusive classrooms. As noted by Eynon and Malmberg (2011), for digital technologies to be truly inclusive, schools must ensure that learners with disabilities have equal access to the necessary devices and tools that are tailored to their specific needs. Furthermore, accessibility of devices is not only about quantity but also about quality. Adaptive devices, such as Braille displays for visually impaired students or communication devices for non-verbal learners, are essential for creating an inclusive environment. As Bejo and Husain (2020) argue, providing access to such specialized devices is key to leveling the playing field for students with disabilities in digital learning contexts.

The study also revealed significant challenges related to infrastructure, particularly in schools with inconsistent electricity and poor internet connectivity. One teacher noted, *“Sometimes we want to use the digital tools, but the power goes out or the internet is too weak. Without reliable infrastructure, it’s hard to depend on technology in our lessons.”* This finding echoes the concerns raised by Kay (2012), who found that unreliable infrastructure, especially in developing regions, impedes the effective use of technology in schools. Power outages, slow internet, and lack of technical support can prevent teachers from using digital tools to their fullest potential. Additionally, participants expressed the need for improved technical support within schools. As one teacher noted, *“When a device stops working or software crashes, we have no one to fix it immediately. We need a technician on-site or at least someone we can call for quick support.”* This sentiment is consistent with findings from Al-Azawei, Parslow, and Lundqvist (2016), who found that technical difficulties and the absence of dedicated support staff are major barriers to the effective use of digital technologies. Establishing reliable technical support systems and ensuring that schools have the necessary infrastructure to support digital learning are critical steps in maximizing the

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benefits of technology for all students, especially those with disabilities.

CONCLUSION

The findings from this study highlight the dual nature of digital technologies in inclusive education. On one hand, they have enhanced accessibility, engagement, and personalized learning for learners with disabilities, allowing them to participate more fully in educational activities. On the other hand, challenges such as insufficient infrastructure, lack of teacher training, and limited access to adaptive devices hinder the full potential of digital tools. To maximize the benefits of digital technologies, it is imperative that schools invest in adequate infrastructure, provide ongoing professional development for teachers, and ensure the availability of devices that meet the specific needs of learners with disabilities. First, ongoing teacher training and professional development are essential to ensure that educators can effectively integrate digital tools into their teaching practices for learners with disabilities. Second, increased access to specialized devices, such as Braille displays or speech-generating devices, is necessary to ensure that all students have equal opportunities to engage with digital learning. Finally, improvements in infrastructure, including stable electricity, reliable internet, and technical support, are vital to ensure that digital technologies can be used consistently and effectively. Future research should continue to explore how these challenges can be overcome and how digital technologies can be further integrated into inclusive education frameworks.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- i. The Ministry of Education should increase access to specialized digital devices and adaptive technologies to ensure that all learners, regardless of their disabilities, can fully engage with the learning process.
- ii. The schools to invest in comprehensive professional development programs to equip educators with the skills and knowledge necessary to effectively integrate digital technologies tailored for learners with disabilities.
- iii. The Government to strengthen infrastructure and technical support by providing reliable internet access, stable electricity, and on-site technical assistance to ensure the continuous and effective use of digital tools in inclusive classrooms.

Consent for participants

Informed consent was obtained from all participants in the research.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest, financial or otherwise.

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